

D4.4

Methods for Quantifying the Dynamics and Feedbacks of Multi- Hazard Risk

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D4.4/Report on Methods for Quantifying the Dynamics and Feedbacks of Multi-Hazard Risk

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Abstract

Real-world disasters show that there are many dynamics and feedbacks at play that are not captured by traditional risk models. MYRIAD-EU's WP4 aims to improve modelling multi-(hazard) risk dynamics and feedbacks. In this deliverable report, we demonstrate qualitative and quantitative methodologies that we have used to quantify dynamics and feedbacks of multi-hazard risk and that provide insights into changes over time.

Our WP4 research explores various approaches, including machine learning techniques to capture multi-hazard dynamic footprints and susceptibility maps and statistics to compare single- and multi-hazard impacts. We also developed dynamic vulnerability functions using Generalized Additive Models (GAM) and supervised machine learning to assess impacts on water quality and coastal areas. Additionally, qualitative methodologies such as interviews and forensic studies provide insights into changes in vulnerability and exposure. We investigate vulnerability indicators to represent multi-hazard dynamics, revealing spatial patterns of social vulnerability and developing profiles for different phases of the disaster risk management cycle. Furthermore, we introduce a quantitative methodology using nighttime light satellite data to compare and characterise recovery from single and multi-hazard events.

Future work by WP4 will refine these methods through local-to-global studies and develop an online database to provide empirical evidence of multi-hazard risk dynamics. Our findings aim to support decision-makers and involve communities, enhancing resilience through pilot case studies and sectoral collaborations.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Risk, defined by the UNDRR (2017) as the product of hazard, exposure and vulnerability, is typically assessed and managed from a single hazard perspective, often neglecting spatial and temporal feedbacks between - and dynamics of - risk elements (Ward et al., 2022; De Ruiter et al., 2020; Simpson et al., 2021 De Angeli et al. 2022). However, real-world disasters show that there are many dynamics and feedbacks that are not captured by traditional risk models. For example, an earlier disaster can increase vulnerability at the time of a second event (De Ruiter and van Loon, 2022). Therefore, the international community (e.g., IPCC 2022, UNDRR 2022) have called upon disaster risk scientists to improve scientists' and risk managers' understanding and modelling capabilities of dynamics and feedbacks of risk and risk elements. MYRIAD-EU's WP4 aims to improve modelling multi-(hazard) risk dynamics and feedbacks. These improved modelling capabilities can in turn be used to better inform disaster risk reduction (DRR) and adaptation strategies, and to support evidence-based decision-making. We present the role and importance of both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to understand and assess dynamics and feedbacks of multi-hazard risk and that provide insights into changes over time (Ward et al. 2022).

1.2 Aims and Scope

This deliverable concludes Task 4.3 ("Quantifying the dynamics and feedbacks of multi-hazard risk drivers") and aims to report on the iterative development and testing of the methods identified in Task 4.1 ("Novel approaches for identifying empirical evidence of dynamics and feedbacks of risk drivers"). The findings from this task will feed into the finalisation step of the MYRIAD-EU project; they will be used to support the development of the database of empirical evidence of dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers (Task 4.4), and they will be available for implementation in the software package and user guide for multi-hazard and multi-risk scenario generation (Task 5.4). In particular, the machine learning methods were co-developed and tested with stakeholders from the Veneto Region Pilot in the context of WP3.

In this deliverable, we outline a range of novel approaches, including several statistical and machine learning techniques, as well as open access data sources, that have been identified for quantifying disaster risk dynamics and representing them in forward looking scenarios. Our focus is on changes in reported losses and damages due to spatial and temporal dynamics in exposure and vulnerability caused by: (1) interrelationships between multiple hazards; and (2) DRR measures taken to address those hazards. We present and discuss the opportunities and challenges of using these methods and data sources for quantifying such risk dynamics. In particular, we describe our research progress on: (1) time-dependent intensity damage functions for specific (combinations of) hazards; (2) vulnerability for different phases of the disaster risk reduction (DRM) cycle; and (3) economic exposure as a function of time since a previous hazard. We also reflect on hazard return and recovery times in current and future climates and learn about the role of DRR measures in risk dynamics.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

This report has seven main sections. Section 2 describes the main scientific developments. Section 3 describes how the methods can be used in the context of the MYRIAD-EU framework for systemic multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment and management. Section 4 reflects on key challenges and opportunities. Section 5 provides insights in the uptake of MYRIAD-EU research outside of the project. Section 6 describes future research. Section 7 concludes the deliverable report.

2 Main Scientific Developments

This section describes the main scientific developments of work package 4 (WP4) for representing risk dynamics in forward looking scenarios. Many of these developments are manuscripts in preparation and yet to be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. Because this deliverable report is public, and to prevent issues related to publishability of already published material in some journals, we provide a high level summary of our main findings, supported by some example results,

Table 2-1 Planned and existing publications. We use the ID to refer to these publications in the main text of this deliverable report.

[Working] Title	Lead	Status	ID
What can we learn from global disaster records about multi-hazards and their risk dynamics?	Wiebke Jäger	Submitted	1
VulneraCity - drivers and dynamics of urban vulnerability based on a global systematic literature review	Tristian Stolte	Published	2
Data availability for supranational urban vulnerability assessment	Tristian Stolte	First draft	3
Urban vulnerability indicators for different disaster risk management phases	Tristian Stolte	In progress	4
Conversations on multi-hazard risk: Qualitative and quantitative insights from MYRIAD-EU interviews on the dynamics of risk drivers and disaster risk reduction synergies in Europe	Nicole van Maanen	In progress	5
Multi-hazard "paired" events	Robert Šakić Trogrlić & Marleen de Ruiter	First draft	6
Stocktaking of methods for assessing dynamic vulnerability in the context of multi-hazard floods	Julius Schlumberger	First draft	7
Dynamics of Vulnerability for different hazards	Robert Šakić Trogrlić & Marleen de Ruiter	First draft	8
Global to local compound (disease) hazards	Zélie Stalhandske	First draft	9
A multi-hazard perspective on equitable adaptation	Marleen de Ruiter	In review	10
EU dynamics of compound hazards & vulnerability	Katharina Küpfer	First draft	11
Multi-Hazard Risk Awareness in Reservoir Dam Operations: Unveiling Socio-Hydrological Dynamics	Marleen de Ruiter	In review	12
Multi-hazards and waterborne disease outbreaks in SSA	Marleen de Ruiter & Wiebke Jäger	First draft	13
A Comprehensive Review of Coastal Compound Flooding Literature	Joshua Green	In review	14
Multi-hazard Susceptibility Japan	Timothy Tiggeloven	First draft	15
Multi-hazards in an unequal world	Timothy Tiggeloven	First draft	16
Multi-hazard susceptibility and social vulnerability	Timothy Tiggeloven	Not started yet	17
Quantifying impact-relevant heatwave durations	Kelley De Polt	Published	18
Regional differences in the impact of heat on public health within Europe	Kelley De Polt	First draft	19
Investigating dynamic vulnerability of tourism	Kelley De Polt	In progress	20
Harnessing data driven methods for multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment: a review	Davide Mauro Ferrario	In review	21
Multi-hazard susceptibility mapping for Veneto Region	Davide Mauro Ferrario	In progress	22
From single- to multi-hazard recovery: A statistical approach using nighttime light satellite data	Sophie Buijs	In progress	23
Machine Learning to estimate coastal risks along the municipalities of the Veneto region	Maria Katherina Dal Barco	First draft	24
Machine learning approaches for multi-risk assessment on water quality: a case study in the Veneto Region	Nguyen Diep Ngoc	In progress	25
A data-driven methodology for identifying multi-hazard events in the present and future scenarios.	Davide Mauro Ferrario	First draft	26

but do not include a full description of all findings. This is accompanied by

Table 2-1, which provides an overview of the past as well as planned publications of this work.

2.1 Multi-hazard dynamic footprints and susceptibility maps

Machine learning and statistical models need multi-hazard impact datasets to learn the dynamic feedback and interactions of multiple risks. However, there is a lack of such impact databases, in particular at local scales. This section provides the description of methods that can be used as a first step in the development of multi-hazard feedback dynamics: (1) DBSCAN for creating multi-hazard dynamic footprints, providing the dataset of most common hazards in a specific region and their spatiotemporal characteristics in present and future scenarios; and (2) multi-hazard susceptibility maps, which can inform risk managers and planners of the influence of susceptibility of a certain region to the different single and multi-hazard events.

2.1.1 Multi-hazard dynamic footprints

This method aims at creating multi-hazard spatiotemporal dynamic footprints for present and future risk scenarios under different climate change projections. The method has been co-developed and tested with stakeholders from the Veneto Region Pilot in the context of WP3. Four climate hazards have been selected as a first test: extreme precipitation, extreme wind, heat anomalies (not limited to summer heatwaves) and droughts.

Unsupervised Machine Learning, and particularly the DBSCAN algorithm, is used to create single hazard clusters from climate gridded datasets. The single hazard clusters are then aggregated checking the spatiotemporal overlaps, applying a modified version of the MYRIAD-HESA algorithm (Claassen et al., 2023), which was developed in WP5. This analysis is carried out on historical data, relying on climate reanalysis (CMCC VHR REA¹), but also for two different RCP projections (RCP 4.5, and 8.5), testing one convection-permitting model, namely CMCC VHR PRO². The input data has a spatial resolution of 2.2 km² and covers the whole Italian peninsula and neighbouring areas; the timeframe selected for the Veneto pilot is 1991-2022 for the historical period (reanalysis) and 2023-2070 for the future scenarios.

Preliminary results show that in the Veneto Region the most common multi-hazard combinations in the historical timeframe are wind and precipitation on the coastal and mountain regions, heat and droughts on the central plains. In the future, and especially for RCP8.5, heat and drought events will be increasingly more common and will be the most frequent combination over all the region. In particular, the duration and extension of heat anomaly events will increase sharply, especially in the summer months. More details on the results are reported in deliverable D3.3b of WP3 (confidential) and will be presented in the planned publication (

Table 2-1, ID26).

The methodology here described was applied to the four climate hazards analysed in the Veneto pilot, but can be extended to also other hazards (such as cold spells or air pollution) that can be identified as events above a threshold from a gridded dataset. It consists of four main steps:

1. System definition: selecting the hazards, datasets and indicators and spatial and temporal boundaries for the analysis. The dimensions of the area analysed need to be chosen carefully, in order to avoid edge effects that can impair the clustering process (Cressie, 1993). Moreover, the resolution of the dataset influences the scale of the application: while coarse gridded data can be useful for global applications, convection-permitting (e.g., 1-4 km) datasets are required to analyse multi-hazard events (and in particular precipitation extremes) at local scales.
2. Threshold definition: selecting the most appropriate (statistical and/or empirical threshold) for each hazard to identify extreme events. This step creates a mask of Boolean values in a space-time cube, which is then passed to the clustering algorithm to create the footprints. The choice

¹ CMCC VHR REA: Very High Resolution Reanalysis over Italy <https://dds.cmcc.it/#/dataset/era5-downscaled-over-italy/hourly>

² CMCC VHR PRO: Very High Resolution Projections over Italy (RCP4.5, 8.5) <https://dds.cmcc.it/#/dataset/climate-projections-rcp85-downscaled-over-italy/rcp85>

of the threshold is a delicate step, because it needs to be calibrated between the need to identify extreme events and limiting false positives, and the importance of not losing the compound interactions that can arise from the combination of multiple factors, not extreme when taken singularly, but leading to compound extreme effects. A combination of statistical thresholds (calculated with percentiles) to account for spatial and temporal characteristics of data and empirical thresholds to limit events not likely to cause impacts is envisioned. The calibration of these thresholds is done comparing the results of the clustering process with impact data.

3. Clustering: application of DBSCAN algorithm to create single hazard spatiotemporal dynamic footprints from gridded extreme event occurrences. In this step, a matrix of Boolean values, representing the occurrences of the extreme events in the space-time cube is fed to the clustering algorithm. DBSCAN is a distance-based clustering, and relies on three hyperparameters: a space-time ratio, that defines the distance in time and space and allows to control the different spatial and temporal extent of the analysed hazards; a neighbourhood radius, epsilon, which defines the neighbourhood in space and time in which the algorithm looks for elements; a minimum Points parameter (μ), which defines the minimum number of elements that needs to be within the neighbouring radius, to consider the point a core point (and thus enable the formation of a cluster). In fact, the algorithm runs through all points in the dataset and looks for core points. Then, it iteratively aggregates points to a cluster if they are within epsilon distance of a core point. Points that do not have enough neighbouring points and are not within epsilon distance of a core point, are considered noise points and not part of any cluster.
4. Multi-hazard clusters: create spatiotemporal footprints of multi-hazard events, analysing the overlapping in time and space of the single hazard clusters extending MYRIAD-HESA (Claassen et al., 2023). Different definitions can be applied to identify spatiotemporal overlaps of single hazard clusters: compound, spatially compound, consecutive and multi-hazard events. Each of these definitions can be leveraged to study specific dynamic risk feedbacks and interactions, for example: compound occurrences can be leveraged to study the statistical characteristics of joint extremes (such as heatwave and droughts); consecutive events offer the possibility to study cascading chains (such as extreme precipitation triggering landslides) or alternating events (such as heatwaves and extreme precipitations). Spatially compound events can help to understand the stress that multi-hazard events can pose to risk management and first responders, for example due to the need to split efforts into different areas at the same time.
5. Analysis: extracting information on the single and multi-hazard cluster duration, intensity, extension and seasonality. For each cluster, the start and end date and the duration are provided as metadata, as well as the minimum, maximum and mean extension. Moreover, the seasonality of the events (e.g., the month/season in which they occur) can be analysed in present and future scenarios, in order to understand changes in single and multi-hazard patterns due to climate change stressors. Moreover, a map of the area with the most frequent multi-hazard pair is provided, highlighting multi-hazard hotspots.

2.1.2 Multi-hazard susceptibility mapping

Susceptibility in the context of natural hazards refers to the predisposition of an area to experience specific hazards and is focused on factors, such as topography, geology, hydrology, land use, and vegetation (Wubalem, 2022). The related planned publications are number 15 and 22 in

Table 2-1. The methodology for creating multi-hazard susceptibility maps generally involves four steps:

1. Susceptibility factors for each hazard are identified based on literature and past events.
2. Supervised machine learning techniques are used to create single hazard susceptibility maps, considering different conditioning factors as predictors and areas impacted by past hazards as assessment endpoints.
3. The single hazard maps are integrated to produce a multi-hazard susceptibility map.

4. Finally, feature importance techniques are applied as a fourth step to determine the most susceptible factors for each hazard or multi-hazard combination.

Examples of ML applications for single hazard susceptibility maps are present in literature, especially for landslides, wildfires and flood hazards (Abu El-Magd et al., 2021; Ahmadlou et al., 2021; Cao et al., 2020; Khatakho et al., 2021). In fact, this method relies on disaster catalogues that can provide Boolean maps of areas impacted by past events that can be used to train the susceptibility models, through the use of Supervised Machine Learning. In terms of methods, Random Forest and other ensemble methods (XGBoost, Adaboost) are widely applied because of the ease of their implementation, their ability to model non-linear relationships between risk factors, their resistance to overfitting and the possibility to study feature importance to analyse the contribution of single factors to the overall model. In addition to these models, CNN (Convolutional neural Networks) are applied to produce multi-hazard susceptibility maps, thanks to their ability to analyse spatial relations from images and maps.

For hazards for which specific susceptibility areas cannot be easily derived (such as heat waves or droughts), a statistical approach can be used to derive susceptibility maps: starting from the multi-hazard footprints, it is possible to derive the probability of a cell to be subject to a specific single or multi-hazard combination. This information can then be paired with the territorial characteristics to understand the influence of specific territorial characteristics to the occurrence of the hazard.

In order to create the single hazard susceptibility maps, a large impact dataset, extended in time, is required, in order to ensure robustness of the analysis. For each event, static territorial characteristics can be easily provided, such as topographic, geological and surface characteristics. However, in order to account for the more dynamic aspects of the risk interactions, some dynamic parameters can be included in the analysis. These typically include meteorological factors (such as the amount of precipitation occurring in the hours before a landslide event), land use and vegetation characteristics (such as expansion of urban areas or changes in vegetation cover due to the occurrence of a wildfire). The possibility to include dynamic parameters in the susceptibility analysis is constrained by the type of impact dataset available: detailed information on the location and time in which the event occurred is required. Most often however this information is not available, and thus the analysis has to rely on only static values or values calculated over extended time periods (such as yearly total precipitation).

The single hazard susceptibility maps provide information on the most influential parameters leading to the probability of occurrence, and can be studied singularly to identify shared vulnerability. In order to achieve a higher comprehension of the multi-hazard events, they can be combined to produce a multi-hazard susceptibility map. The simplest approach is to combine the susceptibility maps linearly. This approach has the advantage of not requiring any multi-hazard dataset, but can only offer limiting information on the multi-hazard analysis because it overlooks all the dynamic, non-linear interactions that are causing the multi-hazard events. With a multi-hazard dataset (such as the one developed through multi-hazard footprints and the application of MYRIAD-HESA) it is possible to train a ML supervised model that takes, for each cell, as input the single hazard susceptibility scores, and learns a multi-hazard score, calculated based on the occurrence of multiple hazard events in the multi-hazard event dataset. This score can be calculated statically, counting the number of occurrences of multiple hazard events in the entire historical timeframe, or dynamically, considering as multi-hazard events only the ones that occur either at the same time or within a determined time-lag. The static approach can offer information on the distribution of multi-hazard events and can help risk managers and local stakeholders to identify the most exposed areas, and plan for resource allocation accordingly. The dynamic approach offers a pathway to start studying the dynamics of multi-hazard events, identifying areas most prone to cascading effects.

One limitation of the multi-hazard susceptibility mapping is its reliance on mostly static variables; the maps are calculated aggregating past impacts over long timeframes, in order to have a large dataset to ensure a consistent training of the ML method. However, a multi-hazard susceptibility map can guide resource allocation by highlighting hotspots and providing a comprehensive overview of hazard susceptibility in a given region.

Within MYRIAD-EU, we have developed a global framework for multi-hazard susceptibility mapping using deep learning, which has so far been applied to Japan as a case study. Japan has been selected as case study because of data availability, interpretability as Japan has advanced multi-hazard assessments, and the ability to apply transfer learning to the European scale. Furthermore, Japan is chosen because of its exposure to this variety of hazards enabling a more comprehensive development of the method. In this study, we focus on the following hazards: droughts, earthquake, extreme wind, flood, heatwave, landslide, tsunami, volcano (volcanic explosivity), and wildfire. susceptibilities are calculated by finding relationships between the hazard and a range of terrain characteristics, atmospheric variables, and geophysical characteristics using deep learning methods or statistical methods.

The results (Figure 1) show that droughts are common in mountainous regions in southern Japan and northern Hokkaido but rare in coastal areas. Heatwaves frequently affect coastal southern Japan and the Kanto floodplain, while extreme winds occur near coasts like Kanagawa, Chiba, and southern Hokkaido. Wildfires are rare due to low Fire Weather Index values over 72 years. Floods are most likely in Kanto's floodplains and low-lying prefectures like Niigata, Aichi, and Mie. Landslides are prevalent in mountainous regions such as Shikoku and Hokkaido, influenced by topography, rainfall, and seismic activity. Earthquakes are frequent in regions near subduction zones like Shikoku, Kansai, Kanto, and eastern Hokkaido. Tsunami risks are highest along Japan's eastern and southern coasts due to its location on the Pacific Ring of Fire. Volcanic activity is significant around volcanoes like Sakurajima, Aso, Asama, and Mount Fuji, contributing to Japan's high hazard signal levels.

Figure 2 shows Japan's multi-hazard susceptibility map, highlighting high susceptibility in Kyushu, Shikoku, Kansai, Chugoku, and the prefectures of Niigata, Ishikawa, and Chiba. Southern regions are particularly susceptible due to heatwaves, droughts, and earthquakes. Eastern Hokkaido has elevated values mainly from seismic activity. Flood susceptibility is significant in Kanto's floodplains, influenced by flood, heatwave, extreme wind, and earthquake hazards. Extreme wind and tsunami susceptibilities are localised to coastal areas. Niigata's high susceptibility stems from earthquakes, heatwaves, and landslides. Proximity to active volcanoes also increases multi-hazard susceptibility, while wildfires have minimal impact.

Figure 1 Susceptibility/signal values ranging from low probability to high probability of occurrence for each of the nine individual hazards assessed: Drought, Earthquake, Extreme wind, Flood, Heatwave, Landslide, Tsunami, Volcanic eruption, and Wildfire.

Figure 2 Multi-hazard Susceptibility Map ranging from low probability to high probability of occurrence.

2.2 Time-dependent Intensity-Damage Functions

This section describes a review of the state of the art on dynamic vulnerability as well as novel approaches developed in WP4. Section 2.2.1 relates to publication 7 in Table 2-1. Section 2.2.2 relates to publication 19 in Table 2-1. Section 2.2.3 relates to publications 24, 25 in Table 2-1. Section 2.2.4 relates to publication 5 in Table 2-1. Section 2.2.5 relates to publication 6 in Table 2-1. Section 2.2.6 relates to publication 1 in Table 2-1.

2.2.1 Review of literature on dynamic vulnerability

Within MYRIAD-EU, we are conducting a comprehensive literature review of studies covering different quantitative and qualitative methods and approaches for assessing dynamic vulnerability to natural hazards in a multi-hazard setting. This review covers a wide range of hazard events, including flooding, droughts, landslides, earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, heatwaves, wildfires, and tsunamis and will be made available as planned publication number 8 in Table 1. In the following, we provide some first findings and insights in the context of flood events to give an indication of the expected information in that publication. For flood events, a complementary publication is planned (number 7 in Table 1) to accommodate the breath of available literature on dynamic vulnerability in the context of flood risk.

A wide range of approaches has been proposed for assessing flood vulnerability. Some employ structured models involving community participation or expert knowledge. Others focus on detailed studies of specific areas. There are also broader approaches that look at how different vulnerability characteristic factors interact with each other, rather than just combining them into a single score (de Brito et al., 2018; Blackwood & Cutter, 2023). Of existing approaches, it is important to highlight the MOVE framework (Methods for the Improvement of Vulnerability Assessment in Europe, Birkmann et al. 2013), developed as “a thinking tool meant as a heuristic that outlines key factors and dimensions that need to be addressed when assessing vulnerability in the context of natural hazards and climate change”.

In general, the approaches used to assess vulnerability can be classified into: (1) state-damage functions; (2) vulnerability indices, and (3) damage matrices. Each approach is designed for different data requirements, complexity levels, application types, and spatial scales (Godfrey et al., 2015). Some methods aim not just to measure vulnerability, but also to identify its underlying causes or the interconnections between different vulnerability aspects. This is, for instance, done via surveys (Alves et al., 2021, de Brito et al., 2018) or system dynamic models (Joakim et al., 2016).

Despite significant progress in flood vulnerability assessments, there are still notable gaps and challenges in addressing its social, economic, and physical dimensions. In terms of physical vulnerability, there is a notable lack of detailed, local data and models that can precisely predict how the exposed elements are vulnerable to flood impacts at the community level (Malgwi et al. 2020). At the same time, the number of studies accounting for multi-dimensionality of flood vulnerability across disciplines and different knowledge systems (Cho & Chang, 2017).

To investigate methods for assessing dynamic vulnerability toward floods, including compounding events and consecutive floods, we conducted a literature review of existing studies. This work does not provide a systematic literature review (e.g., PRISMA protocol), but rather a comprehensive overview of state-of-the-art methods and approaches that feature in the literature to assess the dynamics of vulnerability. We focused on two types of vulnerability dynamics:

1. Vulnerability assessment between two moments in time for various single hazards (i.e., how and if the change in vulnerability between T1 and T2 are captured), and
2. Vulnerability within a multi-hazard scenario (e.g., buildings impacted by an earthquake and then in this impacted state by a flood, population impacted by a flood relocated to an area prone to wildfires).

We also collect the data behind these methods and approaches (e.g., if a study uses dynamic flood vulnerability curves, we are interested in collecting these).

We employed a search query on Google Scholar to identify a total of 712 publications with reference to vulnerability dynamics and floods. Based on a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria, we ultimately identified a set of 45 publications relevant to this research. Overall 45 studies were identified using real-world case studies to assess dynamics of vulnerability. They are distributed globally as shown in Figure 3. Some hotspots can be detected mainly in Germany, Bangladesh, India and Italy. Overall, the number of case studies assessing dynamic vulnerabilities is very low and it is to this point unclear whether the global pattern has any particular reasons. Further analysis is currently ongoing.

Figure 3 Distribution of case studies working on dynamic vulnerability assessment around the globe. Here, we don't make distinction between the scale of the case study (local, national, regional), but aggregate on a country level.

We found several methods for the assessment of dynamic vulnerability in the context of a single flood event (e.g., Meijer et al., 2023; Araya-Muñoz et al., 2017). These are often quantitative approaches in which vulnerability indicators are combined into a single index to describe the overall vulnerability of a region to floods or other hazards. The relevance of the indicators is based on

literature research and the eventual selection of indicators results from statistical methods (to determine importance between indicators, standardise them, and aggregate them) and data availability (Meijer et al., 2023; Araya-Muñoz et al., 2017). An underlying reasoning for the relevance of each indicator is usually not given (Meijer et al., 2023; Araya-Muñoz et al., 2017).

We identified several methods for assessing dynamic vulnerability in multi-hazard contexts. For example, index-based approaches, such as those used by Bosongo et al. (2014) and Tian (2023), utilise quantitative surveys and regression analyses to evaluate socio-economic impacts and household vulnerability. Phifer et al. (1988) use a longitudinal study to examine health impacts of consecutive floods, while Van Verseveld et al. (2015) develop a multi-hazard intensity-damage model to predict building damages. Luers et al. (2003) employ vulnerability curves to depict well-being versus stressors in agriculture. Jamshed et al. (2021) use binary logistic regression to analyse the impact of decreased connectivity due to floods, and Segarra-Alméstica et al. (2022) assess educational outcomes after consecutive disasters using qualitative methods. These diverse approaches highlight the complexity of vulnerability assessment in various contexts.

Across these different methods used for dynamic vulnerability assessment, a diverse range of data types ((semi-)quantitative and qualitative), and sources were used. Empirical surveys and panel data were frequently utilised to gather detailed household and socio-economic information, such as vulnerability, risk behaviour, consumption, and assets. Historical data, including temperature records and damage data, alongside census data and earth observation data, provided essential background and contextual information. Workshops, interviews, and participatory processes engaged local knowledge, experts knowledge and stakeholder perspectives, enriching the data with qualitative insights. Additionally, various global and national databases, such as those from the WorldPop and Global Flood Database, offered comprehensive demographic and hazard-related information. Remote sensing and earth observation data were pivotal for mapping and analysing settlement patterns and environmental conditions. Nevertheless, used data and level of detail (in space, time and characteristics of vulnerability) varied significantly across the studies we found and make it difficult to compare the results of the vulnerability assessments which calls for formulating some best practice suggestions to deal with data scarce contexts, incomplete datasets to capture the dynamic aspects of vulnerability and potential collection of new data. Similarly, most studies did not consider or discuss the uncertainties/biases and other limitations of their used data and its impact on the outcome of the vulnerability assessment.

As such, this work offers a starting point to further dive into the similarities and differences between the different methods and data used but also to compare with the current practice regarding different hazard events.

2.2.2 Generalized Additive Model Approach

Importance of investigating hazards in relation to their impacts

How hazards are defined influences the amount of impact observed (Figure 4), especially regarding the duration over which a hazard's impact is assessed. Events with the same name but different definitions can result in varying observed impacts. This poses a challenge for inter-sectoral impact analyses, where each sector may have its own definition or approach. To address this issue, within the scope of the MYRIAD-EU project a methodology to define or investigate hazards based on when they cause the most impact has been developed.

Figure 4 Schematic overview of the approach used to identify impact-relevant heatwave durations (De Polt et al., 2023; see publication number 18 in Table 21).

Methodology to define impact-relevant hazard durations

Given the research gap introduced in Figure 5, a methodology was developed to quantify an impact-relevant duration and then recommend this timeframe for investigating a specific hazard. These recommended temporal scales can then be used to create time-dependent intensity-damage functions, with duration as the temporal factor.

The methodology consists of the steps of (1) data collection to represent the natural hazard and relevant impact(s); (2) natural hazard events are identified and classified based upon duration; (3) impact metric(s) are converted into anomalies; (4) impact metric(s) anomalies for each event are then aggregated to have one aggregated value per event; (5) for each event duration classification, the aggregated values for all events of that length are averaged to produce a single average impact value per duration that then allows for comparison. To test the applicability of the methodology, a case study analysis was undertaken to investigate heatwaves within Germany and the resulting societal response in terms of health and attention (De Polt et al., 2023; see publication number 18 in Table 21). It was found that within 2 weeks to 2 months the most societal impact was observed. It was also highlighted that duration is an important factor, along with intensity, to utilize when investigating extreme heat events. The results of this analysis support the recommendation that those planning hazard and impact analyses should be informed about the appropriate time period for averaging metrics. Averaging metrics over the most impact-relevant durations will lead to a better understanding of hazard-impact relationships. The methods developed in this study can be extended to other impact metrics, regions, and hazard types, providing more meaningful definitions of climate extremes.

Extension of impact-relevant durations into time-dependent intensity damage functions

Intensity-damage functions are a way to communicate the expected level of damage at a given hazard intensity. The base required information includes a characteristic of the hazard and a characteristic of the damage. Intensity-damage functions can then be considered time-dependent in two ways. The first way is by being input with data, specifically hazard information and relevant elements of risk and vulnerability, that allows the functions to be developed with changing factors over time. The second way is to utilise the recommended duration from the impact-relevant duration methodology, such that the relationships are computed over the duration that is most relevant in terms of the impact observed.

Overview of Generalised Additive Models (GAMs) in the scope of intensity-damage functions

One way to create intensity-damage functions is by utilising a generalised additive model (GAM). A GAM is a statistical model that builds upon traditional linear models by allowing for more flexibility in the relationships between variables. To achieve this flexibility, GAMs use smooth, non-linear functions, called smooth functions, to describe the relationship between predictors and the target variable. GAMs are useful as they are flexible yet still interpretable. Each predictor's effect on the target variable can be visualised individually since the sum of each predictor's smooth function adds to the total outcome of the target variable, making it easier to understand complex

relationships in the data and individual variable contributions. GAMs have been utilised extensively within the environmental epidemiology field. We utilise the smooth functions to create our intensity-damage functions, and within GAMs, we can also use interaction terms to capture the interactions between variables.

Use case of GAMs for time-dependent intensity-damage functions in the scope MYRIAD-EU pilot regions

Figure 5 shows a methodology that we have developed to create intensity-damage relationships in the form of heat-health relationships, where intensity is defined as the temperature of an extreme heat event and health is measured by all-cause mortality anomalies (De Polt et al., in prep.; see publication number 19 in Table 21). The aim is to compute heat-health relationships within the scope of different multi-hazard moisture conditions at sub-national, contiguous regions across Europe. All-cause mortality, provided by EUROSTAT, which has aggregated this data from other statistical organizations for comparability, is one of the only openly available datasets of moderately high spatial and temporal resolution. When converted into anomalies, all-cause mortality can be utilized as a proxy for potential heat-related mortality. The model can be developed with explanatory variables for determinants of vulnerability (i.e., age, employment, land cover type), which change with respect to time and space, to account for variability between regions and changes in input variables over time.

Figure 5 Schematic overview of the approach used to create heat-health relationships (De Polt et al., in prep.).

We only investigate the heat season within each region, which refers to the time when response and mitigation procedures should begin to be implemented. In our analysis, we define the heat season per region as the average warmest six months within that region. Mean daily temperature is used to represent extreme temperature events, as it has been shown to be representative of heat-mortality relationships across broad regions (Lo et al., 2023). Multi-hazard moisture conditions are defined as seasonally extreme values of soil moisture, relative humidity, and vapour pressure deficit. All values are then averaged over 14 days, which is within the observed impact-relevant duration for the health effects of heatwaves in Germany (De Polt et al., 2023). Sensitivity tests are performed with averaging periods of 7 days and 21 days. All variables input into the GAM are listed in Table 2-2. Our implementation of a GAM incorporates one interaction term between temperature and moisture to capture the interactions between these variables and several smooth functions to model non-linear relationships of explanatory variables within the data.

Table 2-2 Input variables into the GAM.

Theme	Variable Name	Resolution	Source
Hydro-meteorological	Mean daily temperature	0.1 degree	E-OBS
	Relative humidity	0.1 degree	E-OBS
Impact	All-cause mortality	NUTS level	Eurostat

We show below one interaction surface, extracted from the model, between mean daily temperature and relative humidity (Figure 6). To get intensity-damage relationships in terms of extreme temperature that co-occur with moisture extremes we must define what constitutes these extremes as the 5th and 95th percentile of all warm season values within the region. At these moisture values we then take sections of the surface to create three intensity-damage, or heat-health, curves/relationships. From these slices/sections we can show that within multi-hazard heat-moisture conditions the heat-health relationships differ. These curves will further be evaluated across the European scale and systematic reasonings in shift will be explored.

Figure 6 Temperature-Humidity-Mortality surface and heat-health curves for the Algarve Region in Portugal (PT15) (De Polt et al., in prep.).

2.2.3 Supervised Machine Learning Approaches

2.2.3.1 Multi-hazard risk on riverine ecosystem and water quality

Supervised machine learning (SML) is transforming how we understand and manage water quality, especially in the context of climate-induced extreme weather events. SML models, such as gradient boosting and multi-layer perceptrons, have been effectively employed to predict key water quality indicators like temperature, turbidity, pH, and total dissolved solids, providing timely insights that traditional methods cannot match (Ahmed et al., 2019; Hamada et al., 2024). These models help identify the impacts of extreme events, such as heavy rainfall or droughts, which can significantly alter water quality by increasing pollutant runoff or reducing water flow, respectively (Zou et al., 2023). By analysing historical and real-time data, SML can enhance our understanding of risk dynamics, revealing patterns and predicting future water quality scenarios under different climatic conditions. This predictive capability is crucial for proactive water management, ensuring safety and compliance with environmental standards amidst increasing climate variability (Ahmed et al., 2019; Hamada et al., 2024; Zou et al., 2023).

Our application of this method in the Veneto Region Pilot introduces machine learning techniques to unravel the intricate interplay between extreme climate events, anthropogenic activities, and river water quality in achieving the Good Ecological Status sensu the Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC (WFD). We analysed compound hot-dry (i.e., drought and heatwave) and wet-dry (i.e., extreme precipitation and drought) extreme events alongside anthropogenic activities (i.e. agricultural and artificial land use), as well as the exposure and vulnerability of river networks and drainage basins (e.g., land cover, river characteristics, vegetation connectivity). The method has been co-developed and tested with stakeholders from the Veneto Region Pilot in the context of WP3. Through the development of water quality multi-risk machine learning models, we assimilated complex and dynamic interactions to explore the synergistic impacts on key water quality elements and ecological status, unveiling the vulnerabilities of river systems with respect to dynamic climatic and human-induced changes. The approach is applied at a detailed level for 867 elemental river basins related to single water bodies of interested according to the WFD in the Veneto Region, considering the characteristics of the corresponding water body for the historical period of 2010-2022. The method was co-developed and tested with stakeholders from the Veneto Region Pilot in the context of WP3.

A random forest classifier was utilised to capture the non-linear relationships and interactions among these factors. The random forest algorithm, an ensemble learning method, constructs multiple decision trees during training and outputs the mode of the classes (classification) or mean prediction (regression) of the individual trees (Breiman, 2001). This approach is particularly well-suited for handling the high dimensionality and complex interactions present in environmental data (Liaw & Wiener, 2002). Random forests are robust against overfitting and provide a high level of accuracy by averaging multiple decision trees, each built from different subsets of the data (Biau & Scornet, 2016). The algorithms have been previously applied to environmental problems and have proven their robustness (Arrighi & Castelli, 2023; Cutler et al., 2007; Grizzetti et al., 2017).

In this approach, annual predictions of impacts on water quality elements of rivers (chemical-physical elements, specific pollutants, and biological alteration), are assessed by binary classification (impact/no impact). Following the definition by the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), water quality classified as good/high is labelled as class 0 (no impact), while sufficient/poor/bad is labelled as class 1 (impact; EEA, 2018). Random forest classifier is used to perform this task. A preliminary set of predictors is shown in Table 2-3. For all models, the samples are split into 80% for the training set and 20% for the test set. GridSearchCV, an exhaustive search algorithm from the scikit-learn Python package³, is used to find the best set of hyperparameters for each model.

Table 2-3 Preliminary set of predictors for the multi-risk machine learning models for water quality

Categories	Predictors	Feature names
Extreme precipitation	Total precipitation	PRCPTOT
	The total rainfall per year from days with rainfall above the 95th percentile daily rainfall total	R95p
	Maximum 1-day precipitation	RX1day
	Maximum consecutive 5-day precipitation	RX5day
Drought	Standardised Precipitation Index 12month	SPI12
	Standardised Precipitation Index 24month	SPI24
Heatwave	Mean daily temperature	TDd
	Maximum value of daily maximum temperature	TXd
	Solar radiation	RAD
	Warm spell duration index: annual count of days with at least 6 consecutive days when TX > 90th percentile	WSDI
	summer days	SU30

³ https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.model_selection.GridSearchCV.html

	Heatwave frequency	HWF
Land use	Agricultural coverage	agriculture
	Vegetation coverage	vegetation
	Artificial surface coverage	artificial
River characteristics	Natural water body	typology_N
Basin characteristics	Basin size	area_km2
	Average Elevation	elevation_mean
	Average Slope	slope_mean
	Soil types level 1 (dominant class)	soil_L1
	Soil types level 2 (dominant class)	soil_L2
	Soil types level 3 (dominant class)	soil_L3
	Soil types level 4 (dominant class)	soil_L4
	Soil texture (dominant class)	soil_texture
	Soil skeleton (dominant class)	soil_skeleton
Permeability (dominant class)	soil_permeability	

To interpret the model and understand the influence of different features, we employed SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values, which provide detailed insights into the contribution of each feature to the model's predictions (Lundberg & Lee, 2017). SHAP values allow us to break down the prediction of a single instance to show the impact of each feature, thus offering a clear explanation of the model's behaviour (Figure 7; Molnar, 2020). Looking at the ranking of features on the y-axis, we can identify the most influential features. The x-axis SHAP values indicate whether a feature increases or decreases the predicted risk, while the colour gradient represents the feature's value, showing the relationship between feature magnitude and its impact. In short, the representation of the SHAP summary plot ((Figure 7) allow us to understand the importance of each feature and their contribution (negative/positive) to the model's prediction. Additionally, we used Partial Dependence Plots (PDPs) in both one-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) forms to visualize the marginal effects of selected features on the target variable, further enhancing the interpretability of the machine learning models (Figure 8; Friedman, 2001; Goldstein et al., 2015). The 1D PDP observes how the model's predicted outcome changes as a single feature varies while keeping all other features constant (the first 2 graph in the left; Figure 8). This reveals the marginal effect of that feature on the prediction, indicating whether the relationship is linear, non-linear, or exhibits thresholds. For a 2D PDP (the counter plot in the right; Figure 8), two features are varied simultaneously, and their joint effect on the prediction is visualized. The plot uses colour gradients and contours to show how different combinations of the two features influence the model prediction of risk ranging from 0 to 1 (numbers on the counters), helping to understand interaction effects between them and on the model's prediction. These SHAP values and PDPs allow us to account for the cumulative impacts of extreme events on riverine ecosystems and water quality.

Figure 7 Examples of SHAP Plots for Interpretation of random forest models

Figure 8 Examples Partial Dependence Plots for interpretation of random forest models

2.2.3.2 Machine Learning algorithms to estimate the effects of climate change on coastal risks along the Veneto coastal area

Global temperatures have risen to unprecedented levels during the last decades, leading to an increase in extreme events worldwide (IPCC, 2023). High population density, combined with interconnected economic activities and interactions of various hazards occurring at different

spatiotemporal scales, makes coastal areas especially vulnerable to climate change impacts. Machine Learning (ML) algorithms have become more prominent as they provide a new way to analyze these multi-risk events, thanks to their capacity to handle large volumes of diverse data and model complex, non-linear relationships between multiple factors. In the frame of MYRIAD-EU, we estimated the annual frequency of impacts along the Veneto coastal municipalities by implementing the methodology described by Dal Barco et al. (2024) and Dal Barco et al. (*in prep.*, paper ID 24). The method was co-developed and tested with stakeholders from the Veneto Region Pilot in the context of WP3.

The input data are composed of total daily precipitation, maximum sea surface height and recorded impacts within the timeframe 2009-2019 for each municipality of the Veneto region.

The atmospheric projections were retrieved from four climate models (i.e., RCA4, REMO, RACMO22E, CCLM) provided by EURO-CORDEX, and their ensembles, whereas the future scenarios of the maximum sea surface height were calculated combining the mean values estimated for each scenario and the residual related to location, day and moon phase.

Machine Learning (ML) algorithms have been exploited to predict the annual number of days with at least one impact in the Veneto coastal region until the year 2100, based on the daily data of local atmospheric and marine indicators. Multi-layer perceptron (MLP) was implemented to estimate daily risk significance per day and municipality, as well as identify the main drivers of risk, thus reducing the complexity of the model. Following the grouping of the daily risk score data in yearly samples, linear regression was tested to estimate the occurrence of impacts associated with extreme weather events per year. The projections of the selected hazard indicators (i.e., total daily precipitation, wind intensity, maximum sea surface height) were retrieved for three Representative Concentration Pathway scenarios (i.e., RCP2.6/4.5/8.5), allowing a better understanding of future impacts based on the considered emission scenario.

Coastal impacts are expected to increase until the end of the century, varying significantly across the different RCP scenarios. The divergence in trends becomes more pronounced after 2040, with RCP8.5 showing the steepest increase, whereas RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 begin to diverge further around 2060.

2.2.4 Stakeholder interviews

As part of the project, interviews were conducted with stakeholders across each Pilot region (Danube Region, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto Region, and Canary Islands). These interviews aimed to deepen our understanding of key themes, including hazard combinations (Theme 1), vulnerability characteristics (Theme 2), changes in exposure and vulnerability (Theme 3), and the synergies and asynergies of disaster risk reduction measures (Theme 4).

The interviews yielded both qualitative and quantitative insights on these themes, helping to bridge the knowledge gap between theoretical frameworks and their practical application for stakeholders on the ground.

Methodology and design

The interview methodology aims to collect complementary information and knowledge about how the dynamic interaction and feedback between risk drivers is perceived and understood by stakeholders and risk practitioners within and across the sectors analyzed in the five pilot regions of the interviews.

The interviews were conducted in a semi-structured way, meaning that there were predefined themes and questions, but also the awareness that each of the different Pilot Leads had the freedom and liberty to ask them in the order and formulation they felt most suitable. The interview methodology is meant to support a screening rather than a systematic investigation of views and perspectives of the interviewees. The interviews were conducted by the Pilot Leads in each region to build upon the trust and relationship that has been established during the first years of the project. The interview recordings, analysis and results are anonymous, allowing the interviewees to speak more freely. Most interviews were conducted in the local language, or in English, to accommodate any language barriers and use of terminology.

All interviewees were asked to fill out and sign a consent form. Interviewees confirm they understand the scientific purpose and ethics framework and that their participation is voluntary, with the option to withdraw or stop at any time. They consent to the recording of the interview and the secure storage of any personal information for up to six months after the end of the project. Anonymized data may be used in research outputs, and personal information will be processed following GDPR guidelines, accessible only to the project team unless confidentiality needs to be breached for safety reasons.

Interview themes and questions

An initial list of questions was developed by Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, with Pilot Leads providing their feedback and streamlining the questions to enhance clarity and feasibility. The final questions are organized along four themes, and the list of final questions can be found below.

Theme 1: Hazard combinations

- 1a. What combinations of hazards are important in your region when considering (disaster) risk [/ in your organisation] [/ in the context of your work]?
- 1b. Why are these combinations of hazards important in your region?
- 1c. Are there certain combinations of hazards that are becoming more important?
- 1d. (How) are these hazard combinations considered when designing (disaster) risk management measures?

Theme 2: Vulnerability characteristics

- 2a. In your opinion, what are the most important characteristics that determine the vulnerability to different hazards in your region?
- 2b. (How) do these important vulnerability characteristics differ between different (economic) sectors?
- 2c. Do you have any examples from your region or cases in which vulnerability (of certain groups, people, economic sectors, etc.) turned out to be different than perceived beforehand?

Theme 3: Change in exposure and vulnerability characteristics

- 3a. Can you provide examples of situations in which vulnerability or exposure conditions changed in your region due to changes in underlying socioeconomic conditions (e.g., economic recession, land use change, conflicts, migration)?
- 3b. Can you provide examples of situations in which vulnerability or exposure conditions changed in your region during long-lasting disasters (e.g., heatwaves, droughts, COVID)?
- 3c. Can you provide examples of situations in which vulnerability or exposure conditions changed in your region as a result of combinations of hazards?

Theme 4: Synergies and asynergies of disaster risk reduction measures

- 4a. Can you provide examples from your region of cases in which measures taken to reduce risk from one hazard/risk also had beneficial effects for another hazard/risk?
- 4b. Can you provide examples from your region of cases in which measures taken to reduce risk from one hazard/risk also had negative effects for another hazard/risk?

Overview of interviews

22 interviews were conducted, with a total list of 40 interviewees (Table 2-4).

Table 2-4 Overview of interviews conducted, the number of interviews, interviewees and the language spoken.

Pilot	Number of interviews	Interviewees	Language
Danube	5	5	English

Scandinavia	1	5	Norwegian
North Sea	3	3	English
Veneto	4	6	Italian
Canary Islands	9	21	Spanish

Initial results

The analysis of interview results is still in progress, but some preliminary findings can already be shared. A full analysis of the interviews will result in a peer-reviewed scientific publication (ID 5, Table 2-1).

For instance, the stakeholders interviewed represent a diverse range of sectors and groups, including private sector companies, government agencies and departments, research institutions, industry associations, and non-governmental organizations. This broad spectrum of participants ensures that our analysis captures a variety of perspectives, preventing it from being limited to a single stakeholder group.

Although we relied on the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction's definitions of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, our interviews revealed that participants often had varying levels of understanding of these concepts. For example, vulnerability is defined as “the conditions determined by physical, social, economic, and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets, or systems to the impacts of hazards” (UNDRR, 2016). However, confusion among participants about these terms was common.

For instance, when asked, “In your opinion, what are the most important characteristics that determine the vulnerability to different hazards in your region?” Interviewee 1 responded that proximity to the sea was a key determinant of vulnerability: “Additionally, the proximity to the sea and the fact that the sea acts as a barrier when winds blow from the south: the sea level rises, aggravating the situation significantly compared to a scenario where these phenomena do not occur.” In our framework, this description aligns more closely with exposure to a hazard rather than vulnerability, reflecting a common misunderstanding of the distinction between these concepts and overlap in meaning of these terms in everyday use.

Here, we describe the results in terms of the scientific terminology laid out in the MYRIAD Handbook (REF). This entails that some aspects were mentioned by the interviewees in a different theme than reported here.

Interviewees mentioned a range of climatic and non-climatic natural hazards and hazard combinations (Theme 1). Table 2-5 shows examples of natural hazard combinations reported for the different Pilot regions. Notably, interviewees mentioned also non-natural hazards, but man-made hazards related to industry and infrastructure, such as pollution and accidents. These examples suggest that interviewees consider hazards to extend beyond the conventional scope of environmental, climatic, or geological processes. This broadened perspective highlights the need to expand our understanding of hazards to include a wider range of threats.

Table 2-5 Examples of relevant natural hazard combinations mentioned by the interviewees in each of the regions

Canary Islands	Scandinavia	Danube	North Sea	Veneto
Storms and flooding	Rapid temperature fluctuations, and snowmelt	Flooding, heavy precipitation	Wind, waves, and fog	Heavy precipitation, flooding, landslides, and debris flows
Fires, avalanches, and volcanic activity	Snowfall, heavy precipitation, and wind	Flooding and pollution spills		Flooding, wildfires

Fires, erosion, and deforestation	Storms, extreme cold, and low precipitation			
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Regarding vulnerability (Theme 2), interviewees described various factors that can influence both social and economic vulnerability. For instance, socially disadvantaged communities may be more susceptible to hazards, while economic constraints can limit a region's capacity to prepare for future hazards, especially if it has already experienced a recent disaster.

In examining changes in exposure and vulnerability (Theme 3), one example illustrates how management practices can influence both factors over time. Interviewee B, referencing the Danube region, noted that over the last decade, areas experiencing prolonged drought have adapted their water management practices to cope with water deficits. However, this focus on addressing drought conditions by ensuring reservoirs were filled left the region less prepared for sudden, large floods. This highlights how shifting priorities in response to one crisis can inadvertently increase vulnerability to another. Additionally, the interviewee pointed out trends of increasing urbanization, infrastructure densification, and expanded logistical operations, which have contributed to heightened exposure in the region.

Looking at Theme 4, all pilot regions discussed both synergies and asynergies in disaster risk reduction measures. For example, in the North Sea pilot region, the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) Convention was highlighted as a positive synergy, as it fosters international cooperation and communication to respond to hazards more effectively. Conversely, in Scandinavia, asynergies were identified due to the reliance on hard infrastructure, such as dikes, which have increased coastal erosion and harmed ecosystems, despite reducing flood risks. The MOSE project in the Veneto Region, which is a set of mobile gates that can be raised temporarily to protect the Venetian Lagoon from high tides, offers a particularly interesting case of both synergies and asynergies. While it protects against flooding and safeguards cultural assets (a synergy), it may have impact on the lagoon system (an asynergy).

2.2.5 Disaster Forensics

The disaster forensics method refers to the systematic examination and investigation of past disasters to understand the causes, factors, and dynamics that contributed to their occurrence and impacts (Keating et al., 2016). It involves assessing various aspects of the disaster, such as physical damage, social vulnerabilities, response efforts, and recovery processes. By conducting thorough forensic analysis of disasters, we can gain valuable insights that contribute to a better understanding of disaster risk.

So far, many disaster forensic analyses have focused on comparisons between single-hazard types across space and/or time (e.g., Kreibich et al, 2022; Borga et al. 2019). Building on the work by Kreibich et al. (2022), MYRIAD-EU put out a global call for multi-risk case studies. Using the community-wide contributions, MYRIAD-EU has developed a global database of around 60 examples of past multi-hazard event pairs from across the globe, including geophysical, meteorological, and hydrological hazards, and that happened within the past 40 years. This database of multi-hazard risk events is being used to assess temporal changes in exposure and vulnerability depending on: (1) local geographical and natural hazard conditions; (2) whether there are DRR measures in place; and (3) whether these DRR measures have any (a)synergistic effects across hazards. These descriptions of changes allow us to adjust existing vulnerability curves based on: (1) local geographical and natural hazard conditions; and (2) changes over time.

For example, looking at Haiti's southern peninsula, which was struck on 14 Aug 2021 by a 7.2Mw earthquake, followed by days with smaller aftershocks including a 5.8 Mw earthquake. Only a couple of days later, tropical storm Grace hit the country on August 16 and 17th. This sequence of disasters resulted in (flash) flooding, additional landslides, and mudflows throughout the region (Amatya et al., 2023; Daniels, 2021; Reinhart & Berg, 2022). Next, the disrupted access to Water, Sanitation and Healthcare (WASH) facilities after the disasters put many people at risk of waterborne diseases (IFRC, 2022). As a consequence, the country experienced a re-emergence of

cholera a year after the earthquake, on the 2nd of Oct 2022, after more than 3 years without any reported presence of the disease. By the end of Nov 2022, over 230 people had died from the disease, and the number of suspected cases had risen to 12.500 (IFRC, 2022).

This information allows us to make changes to existing vulnerability functions. For example, shortly after the first disaster, there was an increase in vulnerability of the more remote areas as accessibility of these areas was significantly impacted (Cabas et al., 2023). A month after the disasters, doctors and other health workers were still not able to reach many of the affected communities (Daniels, 2021). Over 400,000 people were completely isolated after the disaster (GoH, 2021). Based on this, rural housing and infrastructure vulnerability curves to a second disaster can be adjusted to reflect this spike in vulnerability in the period directly following a first disaster.

Next, a rapid gender analysis was performed by the ministry of Women's Affairs and Women's rights, indicating that 43% of the organisations thought that aid distribution was poorly and inequitably organised, lacking adequate targeting. Moreover, there remained a lack of information for affected people, especially regarding accessing humanitarian aid (OCHA, 2021a). Hence, based on this, vulnerability curves for females can be adjusted when working on a comparable multi-risk case study.

Finally, changes in exposure due to a first disaster, can also affect changes in vulnerability at the time of a next disaster, requiring an adjusted vulnerability curve. For example, disrupted infrastructures and road networks, which may cause long term road closures and rerouting of infrastructure but also buildings damaged by a first disaster, change vulnerability of these assets at the time of a second disaster. This is strongly related to the amount of time in between disasters, which influences people's ability to rebuild these assets.

Hence, insights from over 60 multi-hazard risk case studies around the world provide insights into how existing vulnerability functions could be adjusted depending on: (1) local geographical and natural hazard conditions (2) whether there are DRR measures in place; and (3) whether these DRR measures have any (a)synergistic effects across hazards. The information from the study will be used to populate the database of dynamic functions of vulnerability. Challenges of the disaster forensics methods includes the lack of homogenous (local) data and uncertainties caused in part by challenges to collect data in the aftermath of and in between disasters.

2.2.6 A spatial and statistical analysis of global disaster records

Multiple studies have reported disproportionate impact amplifications during multi-hazard or compound events (e.g., see Gill and Malamud 2016; Zscheischler et al. 2018; de Ruiter et al. 2020). These amplifications can arise from several different elements in the multi-hazard context that interrelate with each other, leading to changes in impact (De Angeli et al. 2023). The interrelationships can be on the hazard, exposure as well as vulnerability level and it is widely recognised that disregarding them can lead to an over- or underestimation of risk (Leonard et al. 2014; Zscheischler and Seneviratne 2017; Hillier et al. 2020; de Ruiter and van Loon 2022; De Angeli et al. 2022; Ward et al. 2022) as well as ineffective or even harmful risk reduction strategies (Ward et al. 2020; de Ruiter et al. 2021; Hurk et al. 2023).

This section describes our exploration of the role of multi-hazard risk dynamics in globally reported disaster impacts and is related to publication number 1 in Table 1. To this end, we use the disaster records of the emergency events database EM-DAT (Delforge et al. 2023), which is, to our knowledge, the only publicly available source for disaster events including quantitative information on socio-economic impacts with global coverage. This database is widely used in disaster risk science (Jones et al., 2022) and has been used before for multi-hazard analyses, in particular to classify historical disasters into different types of multi-hazard events by leveraging the information on main and associated hazards of each disaster record (Lee et al. 2024).

We concentrate on 9 different hazard types: earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, landslides, cold waves, heat waves, extreme wind, floods and droughts. The methodology has two main steps. First, we developed an algorithm to identify multi-hazards in EM-DAT. The algorithm uses the information on associated hazards in EM-DAT as well as spatiotemporal relationships between

disaster records. The latter are obtained from GIDS (Rosvold and Buhaug, 2021), an open-source extension of EM-DAT. Second, we performed a statistical analysis to assess potential risk dynamics in reported impacts of hazard pairs.

The results suggest that up to twice as many hazards may have been part of a multi-hazard event when accounting for spatiotemporal overlaps rather than the information on associated hazards in EM-DAT alone (Figure 9). The results also suggest that there are different patterns of how impacts compound from multi-hazards and that these patterns depend on the impact metric as well as the hazard type. For example, Table 2-6 shows statistically significant differences in average impacts of hazard pairs compared to average impacts of single hazards of the corresponding types. While the results differ per combination of impact type and hazard types, there are commonalities across all cases: In all cases, the average impact of a hazard pair is as high or higher than the average impact of a single hazard, while the opposite was not found in any cases. Nonetheless, the results need to be treated with caution, because of the large uncertainties encountered during the study as well as questionable data quality owing to known biases and limitations of EM-DAT (Gall et al., 2009, Koç and Thieken 2018; Moriyama et al., 2018; Panwar and Sen 2020; Jones et al., 2023), highlight that future research should be directed at improving and supporting the information in EM-DAT.

Figure 9 Share of hazards reported in EM-DAT between 2010-2018 that are part of multi-hazards when accounting for spatiotemporal overlaps between the disaster records for different values of minimum spatial overlap and maximum time lag.

Table 2-6 Statistically significant differences in average impacts of hazard pairs compared to average impacts of underlying single hazards (ew – extreme wind, fl – flood, ls – landslide, eq – earthquake). A ‘+’ denotes that the value of the hazard pair is higher than the value of the single hazard and a ‘=’ denotes no difference.

	Ew, Fl		Fl, Fl	Fl, Ls		Eq, Ls	
	Ew	Fl	Fl	Fl	Ls	Eq	Ls
Damages	+	+					
Number of Deaths	=	=	+	+	=		
Number of People Affected	=	=	+	=	+	=	+

2.3 Vulnerability Indicators

This section describes the potential of vulnerability indicators to capture dynamic vulnerability in a multi-hazard context. Section 2.3.1 relates to publication 2, Section 2.3.2 relates to publication 4, and Section 2.3.3 relates to publication 16 in Table 2-1.

2.3.1 VulneraCity

In risk assessments, (social) vulnerability is often represented by a set of indicators. Such indicators do not describe all facets of vulnerability, as they are limited by data availability, the level of

understanding of the local context, and the level of understanding of the theory behind a vulnerability assessment. To get a better understanding of what drives vulnerability, we developed the VulneraCity database (Stolte et al., 2024), the most comprehensive overview of urban vulnerability drivers to date, based on an extensive review of 3000 scientific articles. It contains over 1400 characteristics (= the drivers) that could influence someone's or something's vulnerability to either pluvial flooding, coastal flooding, droughts, heatwaves, waterborne diseases, or earthquakes. Although the database has an urban focus, many of the drivers listed are likely relevant outside the city context. We can now use VulneraCity to better inform our vulnerability assessments, as we demonstrate below (Sections 2.3.2.2 and 2.3.2.4). VulneraCity was reported in more detail in the previous deliverable D4.3 (De Ruiter et al., 2023).

2.3.2 Vulnerability Indicators for Different Phases of the DRM Cycle

In state-of-the-art vulnerability assessments, indicators represent the vulnerability as a single constant. However, if we instead distribute indicators over the different phases of the Disaster Risk Management (DRM) Cycle, we get a constant for each moment relative to the moment of impact. This allows us to implicitly assess temporal vulnerability dynamics. There have been several renditions of the DRM-cycle over the past years (van den Hurk et al., 2023; de Ruiter et al., 2020; de Moel & Aerts, 2008; Baird et al., 1975). We here adhere to the version of de Moel & Aerts (2008), which includes the following four phases and their definitions (based on the MYRIAD-EU Handbook; Gill et al., 2022):

Prevention/Mitigation = “The lessening of the potential adverse impacts of a hazardous event (including those that are human induced) through actions that reduce hazard, exposure, and vulnerability.” (note that this is the MYRIAD-EU Handbook’s definition of ‘mitigation’, but that the term ‘prevention is often strongly related to it, as for instance in de Moel & Aerts (2008) or on the website of UN-Spider (n.d.).

Preparedness = “The knowledge and capacities developed by governments, response and recovery organizations, communities, and individuals to effectively anticipate, respond to, and recover from the impacts of likely, imminent, or current disasters.”

Response = “Actions taken directly before, during or immediately after a disaster to save lives, reduce health impacts, ensure public safety, and meet the basic subsistence needs of the people affected.”

Recovery = “The restoring or improving of livelihoods and health, as well as economic, physical, social, cultural and environmental assets, systems and activities, of a disaster-affected community or society, aligning with the principles of sustainable development and 'build back better', to avoid or reduce future disaster risk.”

To assess vulnerability for different phases of the DRM cycle we apply a range of different methods. In the first step, we try to identify factors that are relevant for vulnerability in the region of interest using the results from the Stakeholder interviews (Section 2.2.4) as a starting point. Then, we distributed the factors over the different phases of the DRM cycle using our own expert judgement. Finally, we add topics that did not surface from the interviews, but which are identified as being important in vulnerability assessments elsewhere. In this deliverable, we showcase an example for the Veneto Pilot, noting that the results are still preliminary.

2.3.2.1 Interview analysis

Participants in the interviews identified several vulnerability factors that contribute to disaster risk and resilience in Veneto. One key issue is the repetitiveness and overlap of hazard events, such as seismic and hydrological occurrences. While the community and local systems may initially cope with such events, their resilience weakens over time, especially when hazards occur in close succession.

Another important factor is the community’s sense of self-protection and risk perception. Many individuals put themselves in dangerous situations to safeguard their property, increasing their personal vulnerability. Governance also plays a critical role in mitigating disaster risk, with effective

emergency planning, proper organization, and regular drills identified as essential to enhancing resilience.

The region's geography, including its topographical and hydrographical characteristics, adds complexity to its vulnerability profile. Poor subsurface permeability often results in water accumulation, making the area more prone to significant weather events. Additionally, Veneto's population density, with many medium-sized cities, contributes to heightened vulnerability, as does the increasing and aging population, which leaves certain groups, particularly the elderly and economically disadvantaged, at greater risk.

The challenges faced by small, aging villages were also highlighted, as these communities are less equipped to respond to disasters. Extensive urban development in Veneto, particularly the heavy consumption of soil for new urban centres, was mentioned as a critical issue that exacerbates vulnerability.

Communication challenges were another point of concern, with interviewees noting that while strategies and plans may be in place, their effectiveness can be undermined by poor dissemination of information. The region's infrastructure also lacks contingency plans, leaving it more vulnerable during disruptions, despite relatively quick repair times.

Post-war urbanization in Veneto has further compounded these vulnerabilities, with construction in hazardous areas, such as landslide-prone regions, increasing the region's overall risk.

These various vulnerability factors were mentioned by interviewees from the Veneto region. As previously mentioned, it is important to note that stakeholders may have varying interpretations of "vulnerability" compared to the scientific definitions we use, potentially leading to different outcomes.

2.3.2.2 Hazard and indicator selection

The vulnerability factors from the interviews are distributed over the different DRM-cycle phases based on expert judgement by the authors of this deliverable. We then proceed in collecting (spatial) quantitative and qualitative data to operationalise these drivers into vulnerability indicators with which we make an overall vulnerability profile for the region (section 10.3.2.3). Subsequently, we analyse this profile through the lens of each phase in the DRM cycle. After that, we use VulneraCity (Section 2.3.1) to add topics that did not surface from the interviews, but which are identified as being important in vulnerability assessments elsewhere. In a future addition to this method, we will try to distil from the interviews whether vulnerability increases between certain hazard events.

A potential future add-on to this method is the use of the multi-hazard susceptibility map - which is currently in development (see publication 15 in Table 2-1) - to find out which hazards are relevant to the regions under investigation. For our example case, we consider heatwaves as interviewees identified these as a relevant hazard in Veneto, and because it is a hazard that is covered in VulneraCity. Table 2-7 has the indicators that we derived from the interview results (see 2.3.2.1) and their relevance for each DRM-cycle phase. Relevance is determined based on expert judgement of the authors. When this method is further elaborated into a scientific article, we aim to go through several cycles of expert judgement with different expert panels. The overview in Table 2-7 is therefore a preliminary list. Data sources are given for those data that we used to develop a vulnerability profile with.

For our theoretical framework, we refer to the UNDRR's definitions for hazard, exposure, and vulnerability (UNDRR, 2016).

Table 2-7 Overview of indicators for each phase of the DRM-cycle for heatwaves. Note that more vulnerability indicators are derived from the interviews, but that for the purpose of this demonstration we only look at the ones in this Table.

DRM-cycle phase	Indicator	Justification	Complementary data sources to the stakeholder interviews
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Prevention/ Mitigation	Presence of a dedicated hazard-management institution within the region	Such an institution proves that the authorities are taking the hazard seriously and that they are working on prevention/mitigation.	De'Donato et al. (2018) Department of Civil Protection (2021) Mangones & Kavaleuski (2024) Regione Del Veneto, Civil Protection, ARPAV, 2024 arpa.veneto.it (n.d.)
	Presence or number of hazard awareness campaigns	Hazard awareness campaigns help in raising awareness and thus increase the likelihood of mitigation measures to be taken.	Mangones & Kavaleuski (2024) De'Donato et al. (2018)
	Green space area	Green spaces help reduce the urban heat island effect.	Urban Atlas Street Tree Layer
Preparedness	Presence of a dedicated hazard-management institution within the region	Such an institution proves that the authorities are taking the hazard seriously and that they are working on preparedness.	De'Donato et al. (2018) Department of Civil Protection (2021) Mangones & Kavaleuski (2024) Regione Del Veneto, Civil Protection, ARPAV, 2024 arpa.veneto.it (n.d.)
	Presence of emergency planning/plans	Emergency plans need to be prepared to initiate timely action when a hazard occurs.	De'Donato et al. (2018) Department of Civil Protection (2021)
	Presence of EWS	Early Warning Systems (EWS) alert citizens of upcoming hazards.	De'Donato et al. (2018) Department of Civil Protection (2021)
Response	Presence of a dedicated hazard-management institution within the region	Such an institution proves that the authorities are taking the hazard seriously and that they are working on response.	De'Donato et al. (2018) Department of Civil Protection (2021) Mangones & Kavaleuski (2024) Regione Del Veneto, Civil Protection, ARPAV, 2024 arpa.veneto.it (n.d.)
	Presence of emergency planning/plans	Emergency plans are necessary to initiate timely	De'Donato et al. (2018)

		rescue/emergency actions.	Department of Civil Protection (2021)
	Presence of cool centres	Cool centres act as a refuge for citizens without appropriate cooling devices at home.	OpenStreetMap
	Green space area	Green spaces act as a refuge for citizens without appropriate cooling devices at home.	Urban Atlas Street Tree Layer
Recovery	Presence of a dedicated hazard-management institution within the region	Such an institution proves that the authorities are taking the hazard seriously and that they are working on recovery.	De'Donato et al. (2018) Department of Civil Protection (2021) Mangones & Kavaleuski (2024) Regione Del Veneto, Civil Protection, ARPAV, 2024 arpa.veneto.it (n.d.)

2.3.2.3 Example vulnerability profile for the Veneto region

Heatwaves have a large impact in Italy according to the Italian Red Cross (Mangones & Kavaleuski, 2024). There has been a national Italian heatwave plan since 2004, focusing on the larger cities with over 200,000 inhabitants and their 'vulnerable' populations (De'Donato et al., 2018) - including Venice and Verona for the Veneto region. These cities receive a two-day lead time early warning message about heatwaves, are advised on strategies to deal with the heat, and are monitored on excess mortality and effectiveness of preventive measures (De'Donato et al., 2018). In the 2023 heatwave, the national health authorities re-launched an old media campaign on climate change and tailored it towards heatwaves to inform citizens about prevention measures and actions for coping. They also provided points of contact for socially isolated citizens (Mangones & Kavaleuski, 2024). In 2024, the "Protegiamoci dal caldo" (Protect us from heat) programme was launched to warn citizens for the dangers of heat and to provide them with information to combat the hazard (Ministero della Salute, 2024).

Outside of the major cities, there is also a regional system of heat discomfort warnings and heat-information sharing in Veneto (Mangones & Kavaleuski, 2024). This system is managed by the Agenzia Regionale per la Prevenzione e Protezione Ambientale del Veneto (ARPAV; the regional agency of environmental protection). ARPAV issues warnings on heatwaves some days in advance, exchanges information with relevant institutes (e.g., on health, the environment, or food supply), and provides post-event summaries of physical distress due to heat (ARPAV, 2024). Veneto Region, with the scientific support of ARPAV, Università IUAV Venezia and Università Ca' Foscari Venezia, is also analyzing how climate change will affect heatwaves and their impacts in the Veneto Region up to the year 2100, as part of the Regional Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation (Regione del Veneto, 2024).

If we look at the spatial data, we find that many of the larger cities are clustered together in the centre/south of the region, along the A4 highway. Smaller cities and towns are located around those areas, but more remote and less-clustered places can be found in the Alpine north of the region. Within the major cities (Mestre, Padua, Treviso, Venice, Vicenza, and Verona), there is 2% - 11% coverage of green space (tree canopies). Verona has the least amount of green coverage - both in relative and absolute terms. Mestre has the most green space overall, but Treviso has the

most green space per square metre. Next to green space, cool centres are also important in terms of heatwave management (Berisha et al., 2017). We collected a spatial dataset of potential cool centres (Figure 10) based on OpenStreetMap data. This layer consists of parks, public baths, (drinking) water points, fountains, community/social centres, cinemas, supermarkets, churches, cathedrals, basilica and general public buildings, as these are places that are generally providing water, built of less heat-prone materials or have air conditioning. There is good coverage of such cool centres across the region, with even several options in the smaller Alpine towns. However, cool centres seem to be lacking in towns in the southern and most eastern parts of the region. Yet, this can also be because the amenities in these places are not yet recorded in OpenStreetMap. When observing these places within Google Streetview, we noticed that they all do have a church, which means that virtually every town has at least one cool retreat.

Figure 10 Overview of major cities, cool centres and the road network in the Veneto region.

2.3.2.4 How does vulnerability evolve over the phases of the DRM-cycle?

The fact that there are multiple layers of dedicated heatwave management institutions, shows the recognized importance of managing heatwaves throughout the DRM-Cycle. Based on the preliminary results, prevention/mitigation and preparedness efforts come in the different forms of early warning and risk information dissemination. Furthermore, the biggest cities have up to 11% of green space, which could be increased to further mitigate heatwaves in those places. In the response phase, citizens could hide from the heat by visiting cool centres where available. In terms of recovery, we did not find any information on how heatwaves cause long-lasting damage to objects and people. The heatwave management institutions seem to mainly focus on preventing/mitigating, preparing and responding to heatwaves, as we did not find information on long-term heatwave recovery strategies.

In the previous section we have seen that the Veneto region puts in effort across most phases of the DRM-cycle in terms of heatwave management. Although the interviews were not specifically heatwave focused (but more broadly on (multi-)hazards in general) we tried to use them to identify important drivers of vulnerability specifically related to this hazard. This also means that lesser known drivers could be at play as well. A driver in this context is “a feature that could alter the vulnerability of an (...) area to a natural hazard” (Stolte et al., 2024). Based on the literature in VulneraCity (Stolte et al., 2024; Section 2.3.1), we have assessed potentially relevant drivers that we have not yet covered and of which the results could be used by local authorities to further inform their heatwave strategies and plans. For instance, VulneraCity shows that outdoor workers may be especially vulnerable to heatwaves. They may not have the option to visit cool centres during their work days, and indeed, a worker near Milan collapsed and died from extreme heat in the 2023 event (Mangones & Kavaleuski, 2024). Citizens could also still be severely affected if they do not heed the heat warnings or if there are communication barriers (Kim & Ryu, 2015; Hansen et al., 2014). On top of that, there have also been reports of tourists becoming unwell (Mangones & Kavaleuski, 2024), as tourists/transient citizens could be unacclimated to the specific type of heat in the region they visit (Hoehne et al., 2018; Hansen et al., 2014). If and how they are being informed about heat risks was not covered the interviews, nor did it become clear from the auxiliary data, which only showed examples of warning the local population (Table 2-7).

2.3.3 Multi-Hazard Intersectionality

Vulnerability analysis in a multi-hazard context is crucial as it reveals the compounded risks posed by the simultaneous or sequential occurrence of multiple natural hazards on human communities and infrastructure (Simpson et al., 2021). Intersectionality plays a significant role, as marginalised communities, already disadvantaged by disparities in wealth, access to healthcare, education, and governance, face greater challenges in disaster recovery, perpetuating cycles of poverty and inequality (He et al., 2019; Hallegatte et al., 2017). Analysing the spatial distribution of populations and vulnerability indicators identifies hotspots where social inequalities intersect with high hazard frequencies, providing valuable insights for formulating equitable and sustainable development policies that enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability. Figure 11 shows how population distribution of exposure to the amount of multi-hazard shifts across different income groups, but also for health groups and education groups.

Identifying the specific vulnerabilities and needs of different population groups gives information for Disaster Risk Management (DRM). Such insights can inform targeted interventions in the DRM cycle, ensuring that preparedness, response, recovery, and prevention/mitigation efforts are tailored to the varying levels of vulnerability experienced by different social groups. For instance, low-income communities may require more robust support during the recovery phase due to limited financial resources (He et al., 2019), while those with lower socioeconomic status might benefit from unmet-needs programs (Bolin & Stanford, 2002).

Figure 11 Population distribution and exposure to multi hazards for different groups of income, education and health.

2.4 Exposure as Function in Time of a Previous Hazard

This section relates to publication 23 in Table 2-1.

Multi-hazard events can lead to prolonged and complicated post-disaster response and recovery due to factors such as physically constrained rescue operations, damaged critical infrastructure, and depleted financial and human resources (e.g., in Haiti in 2021: IFRC, 2021; or Turkey and Syria 2023: CTIF, 2023). However, recovery is still an understudied topic within multi-hazard research (Drakes & Tate, 2022) The use of satellite data is promising in analysing general trends and differences in recovery between single- and multi-hazard events, because of its availability at a high temporal resolution and with good spatial coverage (Kahn et al., 2020). Nighttime light (NTL) satellite data is one of the satellite data sources that has been previously used as a proxy to study economic recovery after natural hazard events, for individual events (e.g., Gao et al., 2020, Zhao et al., 2018) as well as to study general trends in recovery for specific hazard types (e.g., Barton-Henry & Wenz, 2022). Its applicability of NTL as a recovery proxy stems from its correlation with various relevant variables, such as population, electricity usage, and relevant economic indicators like GDP and employment (Chen et al., 2020; Schippers & Botzen, 2022; Gibson et al., 2021; Nordhaus & Chen, 2015)

We have developed a methodology to study and model how recovery after multi-hazard events can be different from single-hazard events, using NTL satellite data as a proxy for economic recovery (Buijs et al., in prep.; see publication number 23 in Table 21). A general overview of the methodological steps is provided in Figure 12, with more detailed explanation in the following subsections. By providing deeper insights into the general differences between single- and multi-hazard recovery, this study can ultimately help to enhance disaster preparedness and response strategies.

Figure 12 Schematic representation of the methodological steps as described by Buijs et al. (in prep.; see publication number 23 in Table 21). Daily NTL data layers are pre-processed into 8-day composites for urban and suburban areas. These data are combined with fragmented multi-hazard event footprints using the MYRIAD-HESA methodology of Claassen et al. (2023) to identify affected areas. A pixel similarity algorithm is then applied to identify suitable unaffected control pixels. A difference-in-differences model assesses disaster-induced changes in NTL intensity over time, indicating economic recovery, after which results are grouped by hazard categories with varying time-lags to analyse general recovery trends.

Identifying affected NTL pixels

For the analysis, NASA's daily cloud-free black marble NTL product (VNP46A2) is used (Román et al., 2018). The research area covers the entire northern hemisphere, covering approximately 135 tiles of NTL data per day, which were extracted for the years 2012-2021. Pre-processing included extraction of cells of sufficient quality, using the complementary quality flag included in the data

and mosaicking of the tiles per day. Additionally, the analysis was limited to urban and suburban grid-cells, as these provide a better reflection of the economic indicators of interest (Gibson et al., 2021; Pérez-Sindín et al., 2021). To extract only these pixels, the GHS-SMOD data of the Global Human Settlement Layer (5-yearly, 1km, R2023A product) were used. To address data limitations due to cloud-cover, the daily data were combined into 8-day composites.

Four different hazard types have been included; floods, earthquakes, tsunamis, and tropical cyclones. These hazard types have been selected because previous studies have shown that their impacts can be captured by NTL changes (e.g., Barton-henry & Wenz, 2022; Gillespie et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2018). Hazards between 2013 and 2020 have been included, as the analysis requires data availability for both the NTL data, as well as all the hazard datasets. The data sources and preparation of the hazard data have been described in Claassen et al. (2023); with the exception for the flood-data, which have been switched out for the flood events as registered in the Global Active Archive of Large Flood Events (Brakenridge, 2023).

Multi-hazard events were defined using MYRIAD-HESA, with a specified time-lag of 3 weeks, including both consecutive as well as compounding hazard events (Figure 13). The footprints have also been adjusted to avoid the analysis of areas that were affected by other hazards that are not considered a part of the multi-hazard event, but that do occur within the area during the analysis period. The final hazard footprints are used to indicate which NTL pixels are considered affected (i.e., the treatment group of the difference-in-differences analysis).

Figure 13 A schematic representation of the event definition following the MYRIAD-HESA methodology, adapted from Claassen et al. (2023). Rather than using the unified footprint of all hazards involved in the event, the methodology fragments the footprint into sections based on the hazards affecting each area.

Analysis of recovery trends for single vs. multi-hazard events

A preliminary analysis was conducted where the average of affected NTL pixels was calculated per time step for all pixels within the areas affected by a single hazard, as well as for all pixels within the areas affected by additional hazards (example shown in Figure 14).

Figure 14 A visualisation of the underlying data used for the difference-in-differences analysis. Here, a random multi-hazard event (event1645) has been selected. It consists of two consecutive disasters; first a flood (fl3032), followed by a tropical cyclone (tc550). Mean log NTL data are calculated for the region that is only affected by the tropical cyclone as well as for the region that is also affected by the flood. Over both areas, identified using the hazard footprints, the average NTL value is calculated.

The methodology will be further refined by implementing the time series similarity analysis, which will ensure that each affected pixel is compared over time to a set of suitable reference pixels (unaffected by any hazards). This approach has been previously applied in the context of vegetation recovery after wildfires (Lhermitte et al., 2010; Veraverbeke et al., 2014) and has been tested for its application in the context of this study, using NTL satellite data. The time series similarity approach uses Euclidean distance measures to calculate a per-pixel dissimilarity measure that is then minimised to select the most suitable pixels as a control. This automated methodology also helps to ensure the validity of the “common trends” assumption: that in absence of the additional natural hazard occurrences in the treatment area, these pixels would have followed the same trend as the pixels in the control area. By using this approach, we can account for seasonal effects of, for example, NDVI and snow-cover that influence NTL intensities locally (Levin et al., 2017).

For each event, we run a separate difference-in-differences model, starting at the full timeframe and shortening the assessment timeline post disaster by each run to assess recovery over time. The relative differences in NTL are then averaged for each timestep post-disaster, to obtain a general recovery curve, with the uncertainty bounds showing the minimum and maximum values that are observed. When averaging, the results are grouped by different hazard types and time-lags, to allow for a more detailed analysis of the recovery dynamics for different types of events (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Schematic representation of the difference-in-differences (DiD) results, which will be provided for individual events (left) and as a grouped result for a set of events (right).

3 How the methods fit into the framework

This section provides an overview of how the methods developed in WP4 can support in the execution of the steps of the in MYRIAD-EU framework for systemic multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment and management (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023). The framework consists of six steps:

1. Finding a system definition
5. Characterization of direct risk
6. Characterization of indirect risk
7. Evaluation of direct and indirect risk
8. Defining risk management options
9. Accounting for future system state

The methods of WP4 are mainly applicable in step 1, step 2, step 4, and step 5, as described below.

3.1 Step 1: Finding a System Definition

The interview methodology (Section 2.2.4), the multi-hazard dynamics footprints (Section 2.1.1) and susceptibility maps (Section 2.1.2) and VulneraCity (Section 2.3.1) can support finding a system definition.

The interview methodology has been directly implemented within the MYRIAD-EU project, by carrying out 22 interviews in the five Pilot regions. We designed the interviews to obtain information on the following topics:

- Find out about the interviewees' awareness of various combinations of hazards impacting their region, including whether these combinations are becoming more significant and are explicitly considered in their work which can aid in the identification of relevant single and multi-hazards scenarios.
- Get insights in the key determinants of vulnerability to different hazards, exploring how these characteristics vary across sectors and sometimes deviate from initial perceptions, ultimately aiding in identifying exposed elements and broader vulnerabilities within the system for effective risk management and resilience planning.
- Understand how actions taken to mitigate one hazard might positively or negatively affect other hazards in the region, illustrating scenarios where risk reduction measures aimed at one hazard inadvertently impact another, thus informing more comprehensive risk management strategies by considering potential unintended consequences. This can provide useful examples of management challenges and solutions

The multi-hazard dynamic footprints and susceptibility maps provide spatial information on the various natural hazards that potentially occur simultaneously or sequentially for a region of interest and can help decision makers to select relevant hazards and hazard combinations for their assessment. (e.g., the co-development activities in the Veneto pilot in the context of WP3).

Finally, VulneraCity, a comprehensive database that offers a wealth of information on urban vulnerability drivers for various hazards like coastal flooding and earthquakes, can aid in the identification of vulnerable elements within the system, such as buildings or populations, and providing insights into broader vulnerability aspects such as economic and social disparities, thereby facilitating more informed risk assessment and mitigation strategies (see Section for a case study using the Veneto Pilot region 2.3.2.4).

3.2 Step 2: Characterization of Direct Risk

The WP4 methods can support the characterization of direct risk in three ways: (1) to aid with the identification of direct impacts, (2) to assess direct risk metrics, and (3) to help identify and understand dynamics of exposure, vulnerability and impacts.

3.2.1 Identification of direct impacts

As part of the disaster forensics study (Section 2.2.5), we are developing a data set of detailed paired event descriptions. This data set offers a catalogue of past disasters including information on direct impacts and can serve as reference for other (possible future) events. The data set is planned to be incorporated in the WP4 database of empirical evidence of how multi-hazards influence dynamic feedbacks between risk.

3.2.2 Assessment of direct risk metrics

The heat-related human impact functions (Section 2.2.2), the framework for artificial intelligence for climate change multi-risk assessment to identify and analyse multi-hazard events (Section 2.2.3) and the nighttime light satellite data approach (Section 2.4) can support the assessment of direct risk metrics.

The heat-related societal impact functions can serve as a method for selecting metrics to measure risk by identifying impact-relevant durations and hazard-impact thresholds by considering hazard factors such as temperature for heatwaves and soil moisture for droughts, or heat-related hospitalizations for health responses. Specifically, exposure to a hazard can be quantified with a hazard duration that best captures the impact metric of interest. Within the scope of the MYRIAD-EU pilots, relationships will be created for all-cause mortality anomalies and multi-hazard heat occurrence with differing levels of excess or a deficit of moisture using the most appropriate impact-relevant duration. From these relationships, thresholds of hazard characteristics indicating an increased impact are recommended to further understand the risk within the system.

The framework for artificial intelligence for climate change multi-risk assessment to identify and analyse multi-hazard events, can help to understand their impacts and vulnerabilities, particularly demonstrated in the assessment of extreme climate events in the Veneto Region of North-East Italy, enabling more effective disaster planning and decision-making. In particular, the applications of supervised machine learning algorithms help to characterise non-linear relationships between single/compound hazards and vulnerabilities of the system. Interpretable methods like SHAP and PDP allow us to account for the cumulative impacts of extreme events on target variables.

The NTL satellite data approach can be applied to estimate the duration of post-event recovery for single-and multi-hazard events. The analysis of recovery dynamics after single- vs. multi-hazard events using NTL satellite data contributes to the characterization of direct risk, because NTL as a measure reflects several economic indicators, thereby functioning as a proxy of economic exposure. Looking at the recovery over time can therefore be considered a way to analyse how economic exposure changes over time after a disaster.

3.2.3 Identification and understanding of dynamics of exposure, vulnerability and impacts

The interview methodology (Section 2.2.4), the database of detailed paired event descriptions (Section 2.2.5), the statistical analysis of multi-hazard impacts in global disaster records (Section 2.2.6), and the vulnerability indicators in the disaster risk reduction cycle (Section 2.3.2) can support identifying and understanding dynamics of exposure, vulnerability and impacts.

The developed interview methodology can help to discover changes in exposure and vulnerability characteristics as has been shown in the application to the Pilots (see Section 2.2.4). The interview questions are designed to explore how socio-economic shifts, prolonged disasters, and multi-hazard scenarios have altered vulnerability or exposure conditions in the region, providing examples such as urban development increasing flood exposure or drought management strategies inadvertently exacerbating flood vulnerabilities. In this way the interviews can inform risk assessments by understanding how hazards impact various elements over time and space.

Furthermore, the statistical analysis of the multi-hazard impacts in global disasters provide insights into changes in impact for different hazard types and impact metrics while the detailed paired event descriptions explicitly describe dynamics of exposure, vulnerability and impacts for 60 different cases can serve as a helpful reference for other cases.

Finally, we are preparing insights into how different social vulnerability are pivotal throughout the disaster risk reduction cycle, aiding in preparedness by identifying at-risk populations, guiding resource allocation in response, informing recovery fund allocation, and directing targeted interventions in mitigation efforts. We explain the relevance and provide examples of how this can reveal dynamics of vulnerability.

3.3 Step 4: Evaluation of Direct and Indirect Risk

The heat related human impact functions (Section 2.2.2) aid in the evaluation of direct and indirect risk. Given that the purpose of risk evaluation is to support decision making, these intensity-damage functions provide information on at what intensity of hazard (e.g., temperature for heat waves) an amount of impact or damage will occur (e.g., hospitalizations). These functions can also provide critical values such as threshold determinations in the case to enact relevant actions.

3.4 Step 5: Defining Risk Management Options

The interview methodology (Section 2.2.4), the paired events database (Section 2.2.5) and the vulnerability indicators for different phases of the DRM cycle (Section 2.3.2) can support the defining of risk management options.

The interview methodology was designed to investigate how actions taken to mitigate one hazard might positively or negatively affect other hazards in the region, illustrating scenarios where risk reduction measures aimed at one hazard inadvertently impact another, thus informing more comprehensive risk management strategies by considering potential unintended consequences. These insights can help evaluate risk management options. The detailed paired event descriptions include information on implemented risk management options and their performance which can serve as a helpful reference for other cases and help identify best practices in disaster risk management. Finally, taking a DRM cycle perspective when looking at vulnerability can help to identify promising options to reduce vulnerability in different phases of disaster risk management.

4 Key Challenges and Opportunities

The main challenge that we encountered in the development of methods for representing multi-hazard risk dynamics relates to data limitations. This especially concerns quantitative metrics and data for vulnerability (indicators), quantitative data on impacts, and suitable data sources for tracking post-disaster recovery over time but also high resolution hazard data. If data are available, they are typically either aggregated in space or in time, limiting the level of detail of analysis. Moreover, impact data are often not available, or not freely and publicly available. We encountered this challenges in the development of all our approaches. Especially the quantitative methods, which are based on statistics and machine learning, strongly depend on the quality of the underlying data. Poor quality of data and insufficient data hinder model development, introduces uncertainties and limits the generalisability of the discovered risk dynamics as well as the applicability in forward looking risk assessment.

While we argue that better recording and accessibility of impact data should be a priority, we identified several opportunities to deal with this challenge. First, mixed methods combining qualitative and quantitative data can be a way to obtain valuable insights in risk dynamics in data

scarce situations. For example, combining empirical evidence from the interviews and vulnerability drivers from VulneraCity, helps in sketching a more accurate picture of integrated vulnerability within a region. Taking the perspective of different phases of the DRM cycle also provides insights into temporal changes of vulnerability without the need for long data time series. Furthermore, descriptions of risk dynamics from the disaster forensics study can be used to validate or reject results of the quantitative methods such as statistical approaches as commonly used in the compound risk field. Second, several novel data sources can support traditional data sources, especially on impacts. For example, the use of satellite data provides an opportunity to study differences in single- vs. multi-hazard events, as its large spatial coverage allows for the comparison of many events. It is also useful specifically in the context of recovery assessments, as data scarcity is prominent in these post-disaster contexts.

A second key challenge relates to the complexity of events and diverse characteristics of the affected regions. This makes generalizing results to similar events in other settings and transferring methods from one site to another difficult. In particular, the methods that we developed for and applied to local case studies (e.g., the DRM cycle vulnerability profiles and the machine learning models) are highly specific to that region and transfer to a different region would require significant work. Similarly, recovery assessments are complicated by the fact that we rarely recover to pre-disaster conditions but have to deal with an ever changing environment. Defining the general concept of recovery (how long it takes and when it ends) is already challenging and added complexity arises due to situations significantly changing after a disaster (e.g., building back better, disaster-induced migration, social tipping points).

5 Take Up Of Research Output Outside of MYRIAD-EU

The work in WP4 is in full swing with its overarching output, the database of dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers in preparation and planned for publishing in Month 45 (May 2025). Therefore, we expect the main take up after Month 45.

Nonetheless, VUA, the institute leading WP4, has already had and will have several visiting PhD researchers who are using and expanding on the research and experience developed by WP4 researchers. These visiting PhD researchers are from the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Katharina Kpfer), the University of Southampton (Joshua Green), the University of North Carolina Chapel Hill (Hunter Quintal), and the Imperial College London (Ekta Aggarwal). WP4 researchers have also been invited to contribute to various review papers based on the methodological work described in this report. These contributions involve collaboration with researchers from various backgrounds from different parts of the world (incl. Europe and the US) and allow for the extension of the insights of the MYRIAD-EU project beyond its immediate scope.

In addition, initial discussions on potential uptake of the methods in other scientific projects or practice have been held with the EO4Multihazards EU Horizon Project, JRC, The Netherlands' Red Cross, and Practical Action. JRC has also invited researchers of the WP4 team to teach at a workshop coming September as well as for a visit at their premises coming January.

5.1 Contribution to the Expected Impacts of the Call

This section outlines the contribution of the work executed in WP4 towards the expected impacts as foreseen in the Call text and the project's Grant Agreement.

"...consensus in better definitions, indicators and functions to characterise multi-hazard risk through enhanced inter-disciplinary collaboration..."

WP4 is contributing to the consensus in definitions by consistently using the definitions of the MYRIAD-EU Handbook in all research output. WP4 has also provided (positive) feedback to WP1 on the developed definitions which supports WP1 in revising or keeping the proposed definitions. WP4 has also contributed to the Disaster Risk Gateway (the WIKI-style) platform with a theme section on *Multi-Hazard Risk Dynamics* which provides a general overview of the tools and methods developed in WP4 and their link to the MYRIAD-EU Framework.

“...enhanced capacity for identification of vulnerable, threatened areas and infrastructures most at risk from multi hazards in Europe”

WP4 is contributing to the enhanced capacity for identification of vulnerable, threatened areas and infrastructures with the development of the methods for multi-hazard dynamic footprints and the susceptibility maps. Both methods can be used to identify hotspot areas that are at high risk from multi-hazards. The multi-hazard dynamic footprint method is already being applied to the Veneto Pilot Region.

“...enhanced understanding of relationships and interactions of multiple hazards ... driven by ... changes on different time and spatial scales”

The main WP4 outputs envisioned to contribute to this impact are the database of dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers as well as the dynamic exposure and vulnerability functions. These will be published in Month 45 as part of deliverable D4.5. Nonetheless, the researchers of WP4 have been actively presenting their ongoing research and results at various conferences, and first papers as well as research briefs have been published. In terms of conferences, the EGU General Assembly 2024 as well as the 3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards and Risk in a Changing world were noticeable events (NHRCW). WP4 researchers showcased their work in 6 different presentations at EGU and in 8 different presentations at NHRCW. Though most of the papers are still work in progress (see Table 2-1), a few have already been published and new publications already refer to them indicating that they have already sparked some discussion on the topics of multi-hazard risk dynamics. Table 5-1 provides an overview of the papers published and their citation. In addition to the scientific papers, we have also published two research briefs to share our findings with a more general audience.

Table 5-1 Published scientific papers and citations as per Juli 2024

Paper	Citations
Stolte et al. (2024): VulneraCity–drivers and dynamics of urban vulnerability based on a global systematic literature review	1
De Polt et al. (2023): Quantifying impact-relevant heatwave durations	4
De Ruiter et al. (2022): The challenges of dynamic vulnerability and how to assess it	47
Kreibich et al. (2022): The challenge of unprecedented floods and droughts in risk management	211

“...better knowledge exchange through platforms such as DRMKC, and stakeholder networks on emergent risks and extreme events (e.g., Community of Users, Risk KAN)”

VUA researchers working on WP4 have also reached out to the different Knowledge Action Networks (notably, RiskKAN and UrbanKAN) to present their work. These KANs have the aim to bridge between science and practitioners and provide an excellent outlet to share scientific findings with a wider audience.

In addition, a first WP4 output that has recently been published, the VulneraCity database (Stolte et al, 2023), is featured by PreventionWeb:

<https://www.preventionweb.net/publication/vulneracity-drivers-and-dynamics-urban-vulnerability-based-global-systematic-literature>.

WP4 also plans to integrate (some of) the tools and methods into the Disaster Risk Gateway developed by WP1. First discussions have been held and ideas been shared among WP1 and WP4.

5.2 Sectoral Impacts

WP4 has not yet had any direct sectoral impacts as yet. However, researchers from VUA have given an invited presentation on the WP4 research to Aon Reinsurance. In addition, it is noteworthy that some of the WP4 methods can have potential impact for the health sector, in particular the heat-related human impact functions (Section 2.2.2). The health sector is not one of the MYRIAD-EU sectors, but has emerged as an important sector in our research.

6 Future Research

In the final year of the MYRIAD-EU project (i.e. the so-called *Finalisation* and *Legacy* stages), WP4 of MYRIAD-EU will focus on the development of an online database of information on - and methods for - risk dynamics. The database will provide quantitative and qualitative empirical evidence of how multi-hazards influence risk dynamics, using the methods described in Section 2 of this report, and carried out as part of Tasks 4.1 -4.3. We also plan to include evidence for these risk dynamics encountered in other parts of the project (e.g., through the storylines in task 6.3) as well as to link to work of researchers of outside of MYRIAD-EU, where possible.

The results of the analyses will be available for implementation in the software that will be developed as part of WP5, and WP4 will support the implementation where needed. In particular, WP5 intends to integrate VulneraCity as part of the qualitative risk index methodology used in parts of the WP5 solutions. The vulnerability indicators can be used in appropriate situations as inputs to the trajectory of a vulnerability function for a particular sector to change. On the EU scale, appropriate directional dynamics can be put forward as part of the indicator weighting when looking at the EU NUTS3 indicators for Tourism. On the case study side, VulneraCity will be applied across multiple sectors where appropriate dynamics are found, to suggest possible shifts in the vulnerability over time on the basis of the empirical studies researched.

In addition, WP4 is foreseeing several extensions and follow up research activities related to the methods presented in this report. In particular, we have the following ideas for future work:

- Application of the DRM-cycle lens to vulnerability profiles to additional pilot regions as well as the inclusion of more hazard components.
- Collection of supranational urban (i.e., containing cities from at least 2 countries) data on vulnerability to assess what data are available for multi-city vulnerability assessments,
- Collection of local vulnerability curves and matching these with the descriptions of dynamic vulnerability in the detailed descriptions of paired events.
- An investigation of dynamic vulnerability with respect to the tourism sector
- An investigation of cumulative impacts of target variables, such as water pollution, using supervised machine learning models.

7 Conclusion

Real-world disasters show that there are multi-(hazard) risk dynamics and feedbacks that are not currently captured by risk modelling methods leading to mis-quantification of risks and suboptimal, or even harmful, disaster risk reduction strategies. WP4 aims to improve our understanding and modelling capabilities of risk dynamics and feedbacks in order to support risk assessments as well as guide the development of effective DRR and adaptation strategies. In this report, we describe state of the art of quantitative and qualitative methodologies for representing such dynamics in feedbacks in forward looking risk assessment and develop new methods.

WP4 has explored, developed and tested several different approaches. First, we have developed two different machine learning techniques to capture multi-hazard dynamic footprints as well as multi-hazard susceptibility maps. These methods support multi-hazard assessment and could in principle be expanded to include impacts, thus covering dynamics on various levels from hazard, exposure to vulnerability, but this is currently hindered by a lack of impact data. Second, we have delved into functions that can represent dynamic changes in impacts and damages. We have reviewed the current state of the art of dynamic vulnerability functions for multi-hazards and developed novel approaches. The first approach is a generalized additive model (GAM), which can model human mortality for different degrees of humid heat. The second group of approaches uses supervised machine learning to assess multi-hazard impacts. We have shown two applications; one on water quality and one on coastal impacts. The third group of approaches aims to represent changes qualitatively. This group includes an interview methodology to extract local experiences and knowledge on changes in vulnerability or exposure due to multiple hazards, an analysis of the impacts of global disasters, as well as a forensic study of 60 paired event cases. Third, we explored the potential of vulnerability indicators to represent (dynamics of) multi-hazard vulnerability. Here,

we showed spatial patterns of social vulnerability and multi-hazard susceptibility, and develop an approach for implicit approach to temporally dynamic vulnerability by creating a profile of different indicators for the different phases of the DRM cycle. Fourth, we are developing a quantitative methodology using Nighttime light satellite data to compare recovery after single- and multi-hazard events. This is a first step towards quantifying multi-hazard recovery, which differs from single hazard recovery.

Next, MYRIAD-EU will further develop these methods in local-to-global studies towards publication in peer-reviewed scientific journals. We will also develop an online database, which will provide quantitative and qualitative empirical evidence of how multi-hazard influence risk dynamics collected and the methods will be available for implementation in the forward-looking risk assessment and scenario software. Findings of our studies will be used to support decision makers and involve affected communities, fostering resilience, through our pilot case studies and our sectoral representatives.

8 Data and Ethics Statement

The information in the deliverable respects the principles set out in the MYRIAD-EU Ethics Plan and in the Data Management Plan.

Appendix

Appendix A Final Versions of Dynamic Functions

This Appendix contains the final versions of the dynamic functions available for implementation in the risk assessment software by WP5 and thus constitutes Milestone 20 (MS20). In the past 1.5 years, WP4 and WP5 have carried out an iterative feedback process in which different versions of the dynamics functions were brainstormed, presented and discussed. The dummy versions were presented by WP4 as part of MS18 in months 21, and the initial versions as part of MS19 in month 30. After the presentation of the initial versions, WP4 and WP5 identified three dynamic functions (as well as VulneraCity library) to be most promising for implementation in the software. For these three functions we present the final versions below. Note that these versions are final in terms of their structure, but that the data values are subject to continual updating.

The machine learning methods are not included in these functions, as WP4 and WP5 see them as stand-alone comprehensive risk assessment tools, rather than functions to be integrated in another software. The reasons that these methods already capture the entire chain from hazard to impact and rather than the dynamic exposure or vulnerability part alone, are already self-contained pieces of software and are not immediately transferable to other regions than the ones they have been developed for.

A1. Changes in impacts from hazard pairs as opposed to combined single hazards

Table A1-1 Statistically significant differences in average impacts of hazard pairs compared to average impacts of underlying single hazards (ew – extreme wind, fl – flood, ls – landslide, eq – earthquake). A ‘+’ denotes that the value of the hazard pair is higher than the value of the single hazard and a ‘=’ denotes no difference.

	Ew, Fl		Fl, Fl	Fl, Ls		Eq, Ls	
	Ew	Fl	Fl	Fl	Ls	Eq	Ls
Damages	+	+					
Number of Deaths	=	=	+	+	=		
Number of People Affected	=	=	+	=	+	=	+

Table A1-2 Table 4 Statistically significant differences in average impacts of hazard pairs compared to combined average impacts of the two underlying single hazards (ew – extreme wind, fl – flood, ls – landslide, eq – earthquake). A ‘+’ denotes that the value of the hazard pair is higher than the combined value of the two underlying single hazards and a ‘=’ denotes that no difference.

	Ew, Fl	Fl, Fl	Fl, Ls	Eq, Ls
	Ew + Fl	Fl + Fl	Fl + Ls	Eq + Ls
Damages	=			
Number of Deaths	=	+	=	
Number of People Affected	=	+	=	=

A2. Heat-related human impact

Table A2-1 Example Function raw values. For all temperature metric values of interest, three separate moisture values are investigated. In the case of relative humidity where lower values equate to lower moisture. The three moisture values include the local 5th

percentile as the low moisture conditions, 50th percentile as normal moisture, and 95th percentile as high moisture conditions. (De Polt et al., in prep.)

Temperature Metric (Tmean)	Moisture Metric Percentile	Model attributed contribution to mortality
0	5	-0.17
5	5	-0.04
10	5	-0.09
15	5	-0.65
20	5	-0.45
25	5	2.53
30	5	5.17
0	50	-0.15
5	50	0.22
10	50	0.29
15	50	-0.32
20	50	-0.17
25	50	2.59
30	50	4.99
0	95	-1.88
5	95	-2.04
10	95	-1.87
15	95	-1.41
20	95	-0.42
25	95	1.98
30	95	-

A3. Single- vs multi-hazard recovery speed and duration

Figure A3-1 Agreed upon format for the analysis of single- vs. multi-hazard recovery speed and duration, as described in section 2.3.

Table A3-2 Format of underlying raw values for recovery functions. These are the averaged DiD results, expressed in %NTL, grouped by different hazard types and time-lags. Actual data is not yet available for publication.

Days from start h1	Single-hazard: hazard-type	Multi-hazard: hazard-type1 after hazard-type2 (<1w)	Multi-hazard: hazard-type1 after hazard-type2 (2-3w)	Multi-hazard: hazard-type1 after hazard-type2 (>3w)	...
8
16
32
40
...

A4. VulneraCity

The VulneraCity database of urban vulnerability drivers for six different hazards (coastal flooding, pluvial flooding, earthquakes, heatwaves, drought, waterborne diseases) is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/8282815>. The last column of the table indicates the type of vulnerability dynamics according to the categorization by Stolte et al (2024).

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